

A Novel Collision Direction Biasing Method for Variance Reduction in Fixed-Source Monte Carlo Neutron Transport Calculations

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ABSTRACT

Variance Reduction Techniques (VRTs) are often required to obtain meaningful results from Monte Carlo simulations of fixed-source neutron transport in a reasonable amount of time. State-of-the-art VRTs typically utilize explicitly calculated space or space-energy importance distributions for this purpose but not only are both calculation and application of these importances computationally expensive, importance is strongly angle-dependent in most practical problems, and this is not utilized in these approaches. A new VRT that biases the collision kernel to preferentially sample important directions without using explicit importance calculations is developed in this study, and it is called the homing transform (HT). The method is specifically designed for duct streaming problems, which are prevalent in radiation analyses of shielding facilities. Clear guidelines for applying HT to these problems are provided, and the feasibility and effectiveness of HT were demonstrated in a single-bend duct problem, achieving a 73-fold improvement in Figure of Merit (FOM) compared to analog transport.

Keywords: Fixed-source neutron transport, Monte Carlo, variance reduction, direction biasing

1. INTRODUCTION

The steady-state fixed-source neutron transport equation is widely used in shielding and reactor analyses to evaluate neutron flux-based quantities, such as dose rates on shielding surfaces or responses of ex-core detectors. In Monte Carlo (MC) simulations, these quantities are obtained as confidence intervals characterized by tallied means and variances, and the variance must be sufficiently small for the results to be meaningful. For deep-penetration configurations, especially those involving narrow voids or channels embedded in thick shields, analog transport often fails to produce useful tallies within practical computation times. Variance reduction techniques (VRTs) are therefore essential to achieve acceptable precision for such problems.

Among the most challenging configurations are duct streaming problems, in which radiation streams through bent voids or low-density ducts that penetrate massive shields. Examples include diagnostic and service ports in fusion devices such as ITER, beamline and access ducts in accelerator shielding, and penetrations for pipes or cables in reactor shields. In these geometries, transmission probabilities are extremely small and the most important particle paths are geometrically constrained to follow the duct, so that even very large analog calculations may record only a few contributions in the region of interest. Several benchmark problems, including the Kobayashi three-dimensional dogleg duct benchmark and the SINBAD/FNS dogleg duct experiments, highlight the difficulty of accurately predicting duct streaming without advanced VRTs [1][2].

Conventional VRTs for such problems typically rely on spatial or space-energy importance maps, generated by adjoint calculations or iterative forward simulations, and then applied through weight windows or similar schemes [3]. However, the importance in duct streaming problems is also strongly angle dependent, because particles must repeatedly scatter into directions that keep them

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within the duct as it bends. Collision direction biasing methods address this angular aspect by preferentially sampling directions that are more likely to lead to contributions in the tally region, while preserving unbiasedness through weight adjustments. In this work, we develop a new collision direction biasing method, called the Homing Transform (HT), and demonstrate that it can efficiently solve duct streaming problems by exploiting their geometrically evident important paths without requiring explicit importance calculations.

2. HOMING TRANSFORM (HT)

The Homing Transform (HT) is a variance reduction technique that biases the sampling of particle directions to preferentially guide particles toward a designated target region. This approach aims to enhance simulation efficiency by increasing the likelihood that particles contribute to quantities of interest, especially in streaming duct geometries where conventional methods may be inefficient or inapplicable.

2.1. HT Theory

Sampling a direction using HT involves a two-step process: (1) sampling a direction from the homing probability density function (PDF) in a local frame, then (2) rotating the sampled direction into the global coordinate system so it points toward the target region. Then a weight correction is applied to the particle corresponding to the ratio of the analog and homing PDF values for the sampled direction to keep the particle score unbiased.

2.1.1. Direction Sampling in Local Coordinates

A direction vector $\hat{\Omega}_H$ is first sampled from the homing PDF p_H in the local coordinate system (where the z -axis is the reference direction) by consecutively sampling a polar angle θ_H (with $\mu_H = \cos \theta_H$) and an azimuthal angle α_H from their respective PDFs.

$$p_H(\hat{\Omega}_H; h) = p_{H1}(\mu_H; h)p_{H2}(\alpha_H) \quad (1)$$

$$p_{H1}(\mu_H; h) = \frac{h}{e^h - e^{-h}} e^{h\mu_H}, \quad \mu_H \in [-1,1] \quad (2)$$

$$p_{H2}(\alpha_H) = \frac{1}{2\pi}, \quad \alpha_H \in [0,2\pi) \quad (3)$$

The single parameter h , called the "homing parameter," controls the degree of bias: larger h values concentrate the sampled directions closer to the local z -axis. μ_H is sampled efficiently using the inverse CDF method, and this is possible regardless of the value of h .

2.1.2. Rotation to Global Coordinates

The rotation matrix \mathbf{R} that rotates the unit z -vector to the target direction $\hat{\Omega}_T$ is obtained using the conventional Rodrigues' rotation formula, where $\hat{\Omega}_T$ is defined as the direction from the current particle position \vec{r}_p to a preset target point \vec{r}_T .

$$\hat{\Omega}_T = \frac{\vec{r}_T - \vec{r}_p}{\|\vec{r}_T - \vec{r}_p\|} \quad (4)$$

This rotation matrix is then used to rotate the sampled direction $\hat{\Omega}_H$ and this results in the final post-collision direction $\hat{\Omega}'_p$ in the global coordinate system.

$$\hat{\Omega}'_p = \mathbf{R}\hat{\Omega}_H \quad (5)$$

A schematic for the rotation process is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The rotation matrix is applied to the direction vector sampled in the local coordinates to obtain the final post-collision direction.

2.1.3. Weight Correction

To ensure unbiasedness of the solution, a weight correction corresponding to the ratio of the analog PDF to the homing PDF is applied to the particle after each direction sampling event. The azimuthal angle is sampled isotropically in both cases, so the correction factor is reduced to the ratio between the probabilities for the polar angle cosines, where $\mu'_p = \hat{\Omega}'_p \cdot \hat{\Omega}_p$.

$$W_H = \frac{p_{analog}(\hat{\Omega}'_p)}{p_H(\hat{\Omega}_H; h)} = \frac{p(\mu'_p)}{p_{H1}(\mu_H; h)} \quad (6)$$

The polar angle cosines are depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The cosines of the angles between the post-collision direction and two reference directions.

2.2. Guided Transport Mode for Duct Streaming Problems

For HT to be effective in its most basic form where a single target point and homing parameter value is designated, the direct path from source to tally must be the most important path. In duct streaming problems with bends, particles must navigate through multiple segments, and thus a more advanced scheme is essential. In this “guided transport” mode, instead of manually setting a target point, the user designates “guide cells” with the goal of guiding particles to each guide cell in a specified order. Target points are randomly sampled within each guide cell for each particle to ensure sufficient sampling of the guide cell region. Homing parameter values can be set differently for each cell, although using a uniform h for all guide cells simplifies optimization significantly.

For duct streaming problems, we provide clear guidelines for applying HT. Guide cells should be placed at the duct entrance where particles enter, at each corner or bend where direction changes are needed, and at the duct exit or tally region as the final target. The same h value should be used for all guide cells, which reduces the problem to optimizing a single parameter and makes the approach straightforward and practical. In the current implementation, guide cells are Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) cells defined in the problem geometry, and target points are sampled uniformly within each guide cell volume. The idea to guide particles to multiple targets is similar to the approach taken by DXANG, another collision direction biasing method, but the angular importance function and implementation details are quite different [4]. HT in guided transport mode is specifically designed for duct streaming problems where the important particle path is geometrically evident through the duct structure. It is not recommended for general shielding problems where importance distributions are complex or spatially uniform. The method's strength lies in exploiting clear geometric guidance paths, which is precisely the characteristic of duct streaming problems.

2.3. Optimization of the Homing Parameter

Table I shows the effect of the homing parameter h on the cumulative probability distribution of the polar angle in the local coordinate system. When $h = 1$, 50% of polar angles are sampled within 64.3° as opposed to 90.0° for the isotropic case. As h increases, the distribution becomes even more peaked toward the target direction. For example, 90% of polar angles are sampled within 39.7° for $h = 10$ and within 12.3° for $h = 100$.

Table I. Polar angle distributions for different values of h .

h	Polar Angle Corresponding to Cum. Probability					
	0%	25%	50%	75%	90%	100%
0	0.0	60.0	90.0	120.0	143.1	180.0
1	0.0	40.8	64.3	92.6	120.4	180.0
3	0.0	25.3	39.7	57.3	76.1	180.0
5	0.0	19.5	30.5	43.7	57.3	180.0
10	0.0	13.8	21.5	30.5	39.7	180.0
20	0.0	9.7	15.1	21.5	27.8	180.0
50	0.0	6.1	9.6	13.5	17.5	180.0
100	0.0	4.3	6.7	9.6	12.3	180.0

The optimal value for the homing parameter strongly depends on the material properties of the collision point and its surroundings, and testing of various parameter values is needed for each problem. Incorrect direction biasing can lead to reduced sampling of important regions, resulting in either statistically valid results with increased variance or invalid results with low variance representing high precision about the wrong mean value [5][6]. It is impossible to determine validity by examining only the final mean and variance, and thus more rigorous tests evaluating the statistical behavior of tallies throughout the simulation are required, like the 10 statistical checks of MCNP [3]. In this preliminary study we manually inspected the mean, variance, and FOM values with particular attention to the RSD convergence behavior following the $1/\sqrt{N}$ trend to confirm statistical validity.

We recommend an optimization procedure that starts with a low value of h such as 0 for analog transport or 1 for mild biasing, then incrementally increase h by small steps of 1. For each h value, statistical validity should be verified and the highest h value that maintains statistical validity should be selected as this typically provides the maximum FOM. This procedure is similar to parameter optimization approaches used for other variance reduction techniques such as exponential transform as recommended in the MCNP manual [3].

3. RESULTS

To examine the performance of HT in its intended application domain, a single-bend duct streaming problem was devised. The shielding region is filled with a high-density pure absorber material with 100 percent absorption probability and mean free path of 0.1 cm, representing a thick shield that particles cannot penetrate. Embedded within this shield is a duct with a square cross section

with 1 cm sides that contains a low-density material with mean free path of 5 cm and absorption probability of 10 percent. An isotropic point source is located at the left entrance of the duct, and the quantity of interest is the volumetric flux tallied in a sphere of radius 0.5 cm at the upper exit of the duct. The duct corner cell and the tally sphere were set as guide cells in HT calculations and a single h value was used for the whole simulation. The detailed geometry is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Geometry of the single-bend duct problem colored by cell type.

All transport calculations were performed with a custom three-dimensional Monte Carlo code implemented in Python (version 3.13). Materials were defined using one-group scattering and absorption cross sections, and scattering was treated as isotropic in the laboratory system. Simulations were executed on a desktop computer equipped with an AMD Ryzen 9950X CPU and 128 GB of memory and 30 parallel threads were always utilized. Implicit absorption was always employed with cutoff and survival weights of $1.0e-10$ and $1.0e-9$, respectively.

Importance distributions were examined using a weight window generator (WWG) importance calculation in analog mode with $1.5e8$ histories [3]. The results clearly indicate that the dominant important path follows the duct, and no particles reach the tally region directly from the source through the pure absorber (Figure 4). This confirms that particles must travel along the duct to contribute to the tally, and that the problem represents the intended duct streaming configuration for HT.

Figure 4. WWG importance calculation results (left: mean values, right: RSD).

A calculation without HT was first carried out with 1.5×10^8 histories (referred to as NPS in the figures) to obtain a reference estimate of the tally and its uncertainty. The resulting relative standard deviation was about 10 percent, and the corresponding 1, 2, and 3 standard deviation (SD) confidence intervals are shown as the leftmost set of error bars in Figure 5. Subsequently, a series of HT runs was performed with 3.0×10^7 histories for each case and with homing parameter values $h = 0, 1, 3, 5,$ and 10 . Here, the $h = 0$ case corresponds to analog transport with the same number of histories as the biased cases. In Figure 5, the mean values and confidence intervals of these runs are plotted alongside the reference interval. For all values of h from 0 to 10, the estimated means lie within the reference 3 sigma interval, but examination of the RSD convergence behavior throughout the simulation for each case shows that the $h = 10$ case exhibits non $1/\sqrt{N}$ RSD behavior and thus is not statistically valid, while the others are (Figure 6). These results are consistent with the expectation that stronger biasing improves variance reduction only up to the point where important paths begin to be undersampled.

Figure 5. Confidence intervals for the reference run and HT test cases.

Figure 6. RSD convergence for $h = 5$ (left) and $h = 10$ (right).

Table 2 summarizes the results for the statistically valid cases run with 3.0×10^7 histories. Using HT introduces some computational overhead, as can be seen by the slightly increased simulation run times, but this is negated by the large decrease in RSD, and the overall effect is 73 times increase in FOM in the best performing $h = 5$ case over the analog simulation ($h = 0$).

Table 2. Summary of results for the valid HT test cases.

Run	Mean	3 SD	RSD (%)	Run Time (s)	FOM Ratio
h=0.0_NPS=3.0e7	2.753e-07	3.622e-07	43.850	133.15	1.000
h=1.0_NPS=3.0e7	4.206e-07	1.563e-07	12.386	150.96	10.681
h=3.0_NPS=3.0e7	4.343e-07	9.119e-08	6.999	181.19	29.319
h=5.0_NPS=3.0e7	4.054e-07	5.260e-08	4.325	185.24	73.298

These results demonstrate that HT can dramatically improve simulation efficiency for duct streaming problems when an appropriate homing parameter is chosen. The use of a single uniform h for all guide cells reduces the optimization task to a one-dimensional parameter search, which in this problem is accomplished with a small set of trial values. The agreement of confidence intervals between the analog reference and the valid HT runs, together with the correct RSD convergence behavior, confirms that the method remains unbiased when properly tuned. The 73-fold improvement in FOM for the single-bend duct suggests that even larger gains should be possible in more complex multi-bend duct geometries, in which analog transport would be prohibitively expensive and angular guidance is even more critical.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A collision direction biasing method based on a natural exponential model for angular importance, the homing transform, has been developed and applied to fixed-source Monte Carlo neutron transport calculations. The method is specifically tailored for duct streaming problems, where radiation must traverse narrow, bent ducts through thick shields and the important particle paths are geometrically evident. By introducing a guided transport mode with a small number of guide cells placed at duct corners and ends, and by using a single homing parameter for all guide cells, HT provides a simple yet powerful way to bias collision directions through the duct while preserving the correctness of the Monte Carlo solution. In a single-bend duct streaming problem, HT achieved a 73-fold improvement in figure of merit compared with analog transport, while maintaining consistency with a high-statistics analog reference and exhibiting proper $1/\sqrt{N}$ convergence behavior for the optimized parameter choice.

Future work will focus on extending HT to continuous-energy transport with realistic cross sections and more complex geometries, including multi-bend ducts representative of actual fusion and accelerator shielding systems. Application of HT to established duct streaming benchmarks such as the Kobayashi benchmarks and the SINBAD/FNS dogleg experiments will provide further validation against both analytical and experimental data. Additional developments will include automated procedures for optimizing the homing parameter based on standard Monte Carlo statistical tests, investigation of combined use of HT with spatial weight window techniques to exploit both angular and spatial importance information, and analysis of weight fluctuation control strategies to further enhance variance reduction performance in practical applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] "3-D Radiation Transport Benchmark Problems and Results for Simple Geometries with Void Regions," Nuclear Energy Agency, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, Paris, Nov. 2000.
- [2] Y. Morimoto, K. Ochiai, T. Nishio, M. Wada, M. Yamauchf, and T. Nishitani, "Dogleg Diet Streaming Experiment with 14 MeV Neutron Source," *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, vol. 41, no. s

- up4, pp. 42–45, Mar. 2004, doi: 10.1080/00223131.2004.10875640.
- [3] J. A. Kulesza, “MCNP® Code Version 6.3.0 Theory & User Manual.” 2022.
- [4] T. E. Booth, “Weight window/importance generator for Monte Carlo streaming problems,” Los Alamos National Lab., NM (USA), LA-UR-83-1138; CONF-830538-2, Dec. 1982. Accessed: Sep. 08, 2025 . [Online]. Available: <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/6085557>
- [5] R. Indira and T. M. John, “Variance Reduction Under Exponential and Scattering Angle Biasing: An Analytic Approach,” *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, vol. 94, no. 4, pp. 323–336, Dec. 1986, doi: 10.13182/NSE86-A18344.
- [6] I. Lux and L. Koblinger, *Monte Carlo Particle Transport Methods: Neutron and Photon Calculations*, 1st ed. CRC Press, 1991. doi: 10.1201/9781351074834.